

Results of Statistical Tests

p-Values

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- all values $p < 0.0001$ are represented by $< .0001$
- significance levels: * $p \leq 0.05$, ** $p \leq 0.01$, *** $p \leq 0.001$
- metrics and respective statistical tests:
 - fitness and solution quality:
 - * comparison of several groups: Kruskal-Wallis test (KW)
 - * pairwise comparison: Mann-Whitney U test (MW-U) with Bonferroni correction (BC) for multiple comparisons
 - behavior distributions: Fisher's Exact test (FE) with Bonferroni correction (BC) for multiple comparisons

Table 1: P-values for Sec. IV-B1: *Emergent Behaviors in Minimize Surprise* – prediction accuracy (i.e., fitness). KW $p < 0.0001$ ***; post-hoc tests using MW-U with BC.

L	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19
12	<.0001***	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
13	<.0001***	0.0164*	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
14	<.0001***	0.0072**	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
15	<.0001***	<.0001***	1	-	-	-	-	-	-
16	<.0001***	0.0006***	1	1	-	-	-	-	-
17	<.0001***	1	1	1	0.2411	-	-	-	-
18	<.0001***	1	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	0.0074**	-	-
19	<.0001***	1	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	0.0033**	1	-
20	<.0001***	0.0146*	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***
21	1	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	0.0001***	<.0001***
22	0.2354	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***
23	0.0013**	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***
24	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***
25	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***
26	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***
27	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***
28	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***
29	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***
30	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***

L	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29
12	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
13	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
14	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
15	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
16	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
17	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
18	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
19	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
20	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
21	0.0206	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
22	<.0001***	<.0001***	0.0074**	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
23	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	1	-	-	-	-	-	-
24	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	0.112	1	-	-	-	-	-
25	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0005***	0.4978	-	-	-	-
26	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	0.0084***	1.0	-	-	-
27	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	0.0116**	1	-	-
28	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	0.0014**	0.0539	1	-
29	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	0.0113*	1	1
30	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***

Table 2: P-values for Sec. IV-B2: *Emergent Behaviors in Minimize Surprise* – behavior classification. FE over all groups: $p = 0.0005$ ***; post-hoc tests using FE with BC.

L	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19
12	1								
13	< .0001 ***	0.0004 ***							
14	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	0.1113						
15	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	1					
16	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	0.7374				
17	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	0.3999 ***			
18	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	0.1908		
19	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	0.2078	1	
20	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	0.0008 ***	1	
21	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	0.0212 *	1	
22	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	0.0055 **	1	
23	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	0.3821	
24	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	0.3864	
25	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	0.0276 *	
26	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	0.0032 **	
27	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***
28	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	0.0013 **
29	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***
30	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***

L	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29
12										
13										
14										
15										
16										
17										
18										
19										
20										
21	1									
22	1	1								
23	0.2046	1	1							
24	0.2713	1	1	1						
25	0.0273 *	1	1	1	1					
26	0.002 **	1	1	1	1	1				
27	< .0001 ***	0.0447 *	1	1	1	1	1			
28	0.001 ***	0.4046	1	1	1	1	1	1		
29	< .0001 ***	0.0034 **	0.071	1	1	1	1	1	1	
30	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	0.1002	0.0439 *	0.5005	1	1	1	1

Table 3: P-values for Sec. IV-B2: *Emergent Behaviors in Minimize Surprise* – solution quality. KW: $p < 0.0001$ ***; post-hoc tests using MW-U with BC.

L	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19
12	<.0001***	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
13	<.0001***	1.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
14	<.0001***	0.3592	1	-	-	-	-	-	-
15	<.0001***	<.0001***	0.0013**	1	-	-	-	-	-
16	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	0.0519	1	-	-	-	-
17	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	0.0015**	1	-	-	-
18	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	0.0005**	0.2402	1	-	-
19	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	0.0001***	0.0066**	0.7705	1	-	-
20	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	0.0019**	1	1	-	-
21	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	0.0129*	1	1	1	-
22	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	0.0003**	0.0795	1	1	1	1
23	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	0.1076	1	1	0.7133	0.0405*	-
24	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	0.6303	1	1	0.0885	0.001***	0.0057**
25	<.0001***	0.001***	0.0622	1	1	0.4285	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***
26	<.0001***	0.0004***	0.0555	1	1	0.0147*	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***
27	<.0001***	1	1	1	1	0.0409*	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***
28	<.0001***	0.3467	1	1	1	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***
29	<.0001***	1	1	1	1	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***
30	0.0001***	1	1	1	0.0032	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***

L	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29
12	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***
13	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***
14	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***
15	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***
16	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***
17	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***
18	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***
19	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***
20	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***
21	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
22	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
23	0.0676	0.1927	0.0118*	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
24	0.0091**	0.0014**	0.0007***	0.6475	1	1	1	1	1	1
25	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	0.0581	0.2453	1	1	1	1	1
26	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	0.0957	0.459	1	1	1	1	1
27	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	0.0002***	0.0018**	1	1	1	1	1
28	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	0.0523	1	1	1	1
29	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	1	1	1	1
30	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***	1	1	1	1

Table 4: P-Values for Sec. IV-B4: *Effectiveness of the Approach* – tests between selected random individuals and random individuals per grid size. Fitness and solution quality: MW-U with BC; behavior distributions: FE with BC.

L	fitness	solution quality	behavior distribution
11	< .0001 ***	0.1852	1
12	< .0001 ***	0.0005 ***	0.751
13	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***
14	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	0.343
15	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	0.0452 *
16	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	0.0011 **
17	< .0001 ***	0.8047	0.0001 ***
18	< .0001 ***	0.2132	< .0001 ***
19	< .0001 ***	1	< .0001 ***
20	< .0001 ***	1	< .0001 ***
21	< .0001 ***	0.9683	< .0001 ***
22	< .0001 ***	1	0.0001 ***
23	< .0001 ***	0.0256 *	0.0001 ***
24	< .0001 ***	0.0046 **	< .0001 ***
25	< .0001 ***	0.0049 **	0.0028 **
26	< .0001 ***	0.0138 *	< .0001 ***
27	< .0001 ***	0.0415 *	< .0001 ***
28	< .0001 ***	0.1276	0.0007 ***
29	< .0001 ***	0.0008 ***	< .0001 ***
30	< .0001 ***	0.0035 **	0.0007 ***

Table 5: P-Values and odds ratio for Sec. IV-B4: *Effectiveness of the approach* – tests between selected random individuals and random individuals per structure type. FE with BC.

	p-value	odds ratio
clustering	< .0001 ***	0.1782
aggregation	0.0047 **	1.5241
pairs	1	0.999
lines	0.008 **	1.7388
loose grouping	0.7857	0.9505
squares	1	0
random dispersion	< .0001 ***	2.144
triangular lattice	0.0038 **	∞
swirls	1	∞

Table 6: P-Values for Sec. IV-B4: *Effectiveness of the Approach* – tests between best evolved individuals (minimize surprise) and random individuals per grid size. Fitness and solution quality: MW-U with BC; behavior distributions: FE with BC.

L	fitness	solution quality	behavior distribution
11	< .0001 ***	0.0502	1
12	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***
13	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***
14	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	0.0024 **
15	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	0.0015 **
16	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***
17	< .0001 ***	0.0016 **	0.0015 **
18	< .0001 ***	0.0008 ***	< .0001 ***
19	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***
20	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	0.0001 ***
21	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***
22	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***
23	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	0.0181 *
24	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***
25	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	0.0068 **
26	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	0.001 ***
27	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***
28	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***
29	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***
30	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***

Table 7: P-Values and odds ratio for Sec. IV-B4: *Effectiveness of the approach* – tests between best evolved individuals (minimize surprise) and random individuals per structure type. FE with BC.

	p-value	odds ratio
clustering	< .0001 ***	0.1564
aggregation	< .0001 ***	1.826
pairs	< .0001 ***	2.1259
lines	< .0001 ***	2.4624
loose grouping	0.7285	0.6996
squares	0.2785	∞
random dispersion	< .0001 ***	1.5369
triangular lattice	0.0171 *	∞
swirls	1	∞

Table 8: P-Values for Sec. IV-B4: *Effectiveness of the Approach* – tests between best evolved individuals (minimize surprise) and selected random individuals per grid size. Fitness and solution quality: MW-U with BC; behavior distributions: FE with BC.

L	fitness	solution quality	behavior distribution
11	< .0001 ***	1	1
12	< .0001 ***	0.5898	0.0181 *
13	< .0001 ***	1	1
14	< .0001 ***	1	1
15	< .0001 ***	1	1
16	< .0001 ***	0.8233	1
17	< .0001 ***	1	1
18	< .0001 ***	1	1
19	< .0001 ***	0.0015 **	1
20	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	0.0172 *
21	< .0001 ***	0.0006 ***	1
22	< .0001 ***	0.0046 **	0.6815
23	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	1
24	< .0001 ***	0.0038 **	1
25	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	1
26	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	1
27	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	1
28	< .0001 ***	0.0004 ***	1
29	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	1
30	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	1

Table 9: P-Values and odds ratio for Sec. IV-B4: *Effectiveness of the approach* – tests between selected random individuals and best evolved individuals (minimize surprise) per structure type. FE with BC.

	p-value	odds ratio
clustering	0.436	1.1393
aggregation	0.1731	0.8348
pairs	< .0001 ***	0.47
lines	0.011 *	0.7061
loose grouping	0.141	1.3587
squares	0.0309 *	0
random dispersion	0.0002 ***	1.3949
triangular lattice	1	0.997
swirls	1	0.997

Table 10: P-values for Sec. IV-C: *Behavioral Diversity of Minimize Surprise in Comparison to Novelty Search* (N-SVA & N-SVQ). Solution quality: MW-U with BC; behavior distributions: FE with BC.

	15 × 15	20 × 20
solution quality	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***
behavior distribution	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***

Table 11: P-values for Sec. IV-D1: *Robustness of Behaviors – Sensor Noise*. Prediction accuracy (i.e., fitness). KW $p < 0.0001$ ***; post-hoc tests using MW-U with BC. 15 × 15 grid.

	0%	5%	10%
5%	0.2945	-	-
10%	1	0.0022 **	-
15%	0.0256 *	< .0001 ***	0.0002 ***

Table 12: P-values for Sec. IV-D1: *Robustness of Behaviors – Sensor Noise*. Prediction accuracy (i.e., fitness). KW: $p < 0.0001$ ***; post-hoc tests using MW-U with BC. 20 × 20 grid.

	0%	5%	10%
5%	0.0156 *	-	-
10%	< .0001 ***	0.0001 ***	-
15%	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***

Table 13: P-values for Sec. IV-E1: *Scalability in Swarm Density – Comparison of the Best Evolved Individuals of the 16×16 Grid with their Reruns in Different Swarm Densities*. Fitness and solution quality: MW-U with BC; behavior distributions: FE with BC.

L	fitness	solution quality	behavior distribution
11	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***
12	< .0001 ***	0.0054 **	< .0001 ***
13	0.0005 ***	1	0.4006
14	1	1	1
15	1	1	1
16	-	-	-
17	0.4085	1	1
18	0.5532	1	1
19	1	1	1
20	1	1	1
21	1	1	1
22	1	1	0.3783
23	1	1	0.1261
24	1	1	0.0545
25	1	1	0.0059 **
26	1	1	0.0201 *
27	1	1	0.0154 *
28	1	1	0.01 *
29	1	1	0.0025 **
30	1	1	0.0022 **

Table 14: P-values for Sec. IV-E2: *Scalability in Swarm Density – Comparison of Reruns of the Best Evolved Individuals of the 16×16 grid with the Best Evolved Individuals of the Respective Swarm Density*. Fitness and solution quality: MW-U with BC; behavior distributions: FE with BC.

L	fitness	solution quality	behavior distribution
11	< .0001 ***	0.8901	1
12	< .0001 ***	0.0731	0.0002 ***
13	< .0001 ***	0.0636	0.0008 ***
14	1	1	1
15	0.1001	1	1
16	-	-	-
17	1	0.0128 *	0.625
18	0.0029 **	0.0037 **	< .0001 ***
19	0.0015 **	0.039 *	< .0001 ***
20	< .0001 ***	0.196	< .0001 ***
21	< .0001 ***	0.2337	< .0001 ***
22	< .0001 ***	1	< .0001 ***
23	< .0001 ***	1	< .0001 ***
24	< .0001 ***	1	< .0001 ***
25	< .0001 ***	0.0285 *	< .0001 ***
26	< .0001 ***	0.0051 **	< .0001 ***
27	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***
28	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***
29	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***
30	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***

Table 15: P-values for Sec. IV-G: *Hyperparameter Optimization*. Evaluation length in time steps – fitness. KW: $p < 0.0001$ ***; post-hoc tests using MW-U with BC. 15 × 15 grid.

	50	100	200	300	400
100	1	-	-	-	-
200	0.2322	0.49	-	-	-
300	0.008 **	0.01254 *	1	-	-
400	0.0012 **	0.0006 ***	1	1	-
500	0.3163	0.7364	1	1	1

Table 16: P-values for Sec. IV-G: *Hyperparameter Optimization*. Generations – fitness. KW: $p = 0.0002$ ***; post-hoc tests using MW-U with BC. 20×20 grid.

	50	60	70	80	90
60	1	-	-	-	-
70	1	1	-	-	-
80	0.11	0.11	0.6893	-	-
90	0.008 **	0.0056 **	0.0396 *	1	-
100	0.3949	0.0640	0.4562	1	1

Table 17: P-values for Sec. IV-G: *Hyperparameter Optimization*. Population size – fitness. KW: $p < 0.0001$ ***; post-hoc tests using MW-U with BC. 20×20 grid.

	10	20	30	40	50	60	70
20	0.3694	-	-	-	-	-	-
30	0.1088	1	-	-	-	-	-
40	0.0548	1	1	-	-	-	-
50	0.0132 *	1	1	1	-	-	-
60	0.0015 **	1	0.914	1	1	-	-
70	0.0004 ***	0.5902	0.3694	1	1	1	-
80	0.0005 ***	0.5902	0.3138	1	1	1	1

Table 18: P-values for Sec. IV-G: *Hyperparameter Optimization*. Mutation rate – fitness. KW: $p < 0.0001$ ***; post-hoc tests using MW-U with BC. 15×15 grid.

	0.0001	0.0003 **	0.001	0.0005	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.04	0.05	0.07	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5
0.001	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨
0.005	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨
0.01	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨
0.02	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨
0.03	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨
0.04	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨
0.05	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨
0.07	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨
0.1	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨
0.2	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨
0.3	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨
0.4	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨
0.5	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨
0.6	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨	∨

Table 19: P-values for Sec. IV-G: *Hyperparameter Optimization*. Mutation rate – fitness. KW: $p < 0.0001$ ***; post-hoc tests using MW-U with BC. 20×20 grid.

	0.0001	0.001	0.005	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.04	0.05	0.07	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5
0.001	0.044 *													
0.005	< .0001 ***	1												
0.01	< .0001 ***	0.044 *	1											
0.02	< .0001 ***	0.0012 ***	0.64522	1										
0.03	< .0001 ***	0.0003 ***	0.1507	1										
0.04	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	0.0001 ***	0.5387										
0.05	< .0001 ***	0.0012 ***	0.4915	1										
0.07	< .0001 ***	0.0026 **	0.7051	1										
0.1	< .0001 ***	0.001 **	0.4915	1										
0.2	< .0001 ***	< .0001 ***	0.0055 **	1										
0.3	< .0001 ***	0.0005 ***	0.4079	1										
0.4	< .0001 ***	0.0055 **	1	1			0.0239 *							
0.5	< .0001 ***	0.0391 *	1	1			0.0307 **							
0.6	< .0001 ***	0.0625	1	1			1							

Table 20: P-values for Sec. IV-G: *Hyperparameter Optimization*. Population size (P) + generations (G) + mutation rate (M) – fitness. KW: $p < 0.0001$ ***; post-hoc tests using MW-U with BC. 15×15 grid.

		P 100 G 50								
		M 0.01	M 0.02	M 0.03	M 0.04	M 0.05	M 0.07	M 0.1	M 0.2	M 0.3
P 100 G 50	M 0.02	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.03	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.04	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
P 10 G 500	M 0.01	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.02	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.03	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
P 20 G 250	M 0.01	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.02	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.03	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
P 25 G 200	M 0.01	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.02	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.03	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
P 40 G 125	M 0.01	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.02	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.03	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
P 50 G 100	M 0.01	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.02	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.03	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1

		P 10 G 500										
		M 0.01	M 0.02	M 0.03	M 0.04	M 0.05	M 0.07	M 0.1	M 0.2	M 0.3		
P 100 G 50	M 0.02	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.03	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.04	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.05	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
P 10 G 500	M 0.01	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.02	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.03	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.04	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
P 20 G 250	M 0.01	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.02	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.03	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.04	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
P 25 G 200	M 0.01	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.02	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.03	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.04	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
P 40 G 125	M 0.01	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.02	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.03	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.04	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
P 50 G 100	M 0.01	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.02	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.03	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.04	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

		P 20 G 250										
		M 0.01	M 0.02	M 0.03	M 0.04	M 0.05	M 0.07	M 0.1	M 0.2	M 0.3		
P 100 G 50	M 0.02	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.03	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.04	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.05	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.07	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
P 10 G 500	M 0.2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.01	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.02	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.03	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.04	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
P 20 G 250	M 0.05	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.07	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.01	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
P 25 G 200	M 0.02	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.03	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.04	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.05	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.07	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
P 40 G 125	M 0.2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.3	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.01	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.02	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.03	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.04	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
P 50 G 100	M 0.05	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.07	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.3	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.01	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
M 0.02	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
M 0.03	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
M 0.04	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
M 0.05	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
M 0.07	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
M 0.1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
M 0.2	0.6755	0.5326	0.0415 *	0.472	0.3258	1	1	1	1	1	1	
M 0.3	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	

		P 25 G 200									
		M 0.01	M 0.02	M 0.03	M 0.04	M 0.05	M 0.07	M 0.1	M 0.2	M 0.3	
P 100 G 50	M 0.02	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.03	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.04	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
P 10 G 500	M 0.05	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.07	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
P 20 G 250	M 0.2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.01	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
P 25 G 200	M 0.02	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.03	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.04	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
P 40 G 125	M 0.05	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.07	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
P 50 G 100	M 0.2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.01	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
P 100 G 50	M 0.02	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.03	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.04	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
P 25 G 200	M 0.05	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.07	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
P 40 G 125	M 0.2	1	0.3692	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.3	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.01	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
P 50 G 100	M 0.02	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.03	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.04	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
P 100 G 50	M 0.05	1	0.5326	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.07	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
P 25 G 200	M 0.2	1	0.5326	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.3	1	0.007**	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.01	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
P 40 G 125	M 0.02	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.03	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.04	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
P 50 G 100	M 0.05	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.07	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
P 100 G 50	M 0.2	1	0.1303	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.3	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.01	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1

	M 0.01	M 0.02	M 0.03	M 0.04	M 0.05	M 0.07	M 0.1	M 0.2	M 0.3
P 100 G 50	M 0.02	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.03	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.04	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.05	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.07	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
P 10 G 500	M 0.2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.01	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.02	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.03	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.04	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
P 20 G 250	M 0.05	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.07	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.01	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
P 25 G 200	M 0.02	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.03	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.04	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.05	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.07	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
P 40 G 125	M 0.2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.01	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.02	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.03	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.04	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
P 50 G 100	M 0.05	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.07	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.3	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.01	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
P 40 G 125	M 0.02	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.03	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.04	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.05	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.07	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
P 50 G 100	M 0.2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.3	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.01	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.02	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.03	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.04	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
P 50 G 100	M 0.05	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.07	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.3	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.01	1	1	1	1	0.6002	1	1	1

	M 0.01	M 0.02	M 0.03	M 0.04	M 0.05	M 0.07	M 0.1	M 0.2
P 100 G 50	M 0.02 M 0.03 M 0.04 M 0.05 M 0.07 M 0.1 M 0.2 M 0.3	- - - - - - - -						
P 10 G 500	M 0.01 M 0.02 M 0.03 M 0.04 M 0.05 M 0.07 M 0.1 M 0.2 M 0.3	- - - - - - - -						
P 20 G 250	M 0.01 M 0.02 M 0.03 M 0.04 M 0.05 M 0.07 M 0.1 M 0.2 M 0.3	- - - - - - - -						
P 25 G 200	M 0.01 M 0.02 M 0.03 M 0.04 M 0.05 M 0.07 M 0.1 M 0.2 M 0.3	- - - - - - - -						
P 40 G 125	M 0.01 M 0.02 M 0.03 M 0.04 M 0.05 M 0.07 M 0.1 M 0.2 M 0.3	- - - - - - - -						
P 50 G 100	M 0.01 M 0.02 M 0.03 M 0.04 M 0.05 M 0.07 M 0.1 M 0.2 M 0.3	1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1	- 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1	- 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1	- 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1	- 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1	1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1	1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1

Table 21: P-values for Sec. IV-G: *Hyperparameter Optimization*. Population size (P) + generations (G) + mutation rate (M) – fitness. KW: $p < 0.0001$ ***; post-hoc tests using MW-U with BC. 20×20 grid.

		P 100 G 50									
		M 0.01	M 0.02	M 0.03	M 0.04	M 0.05	M 0.07	M 0.1	M 0.2	M 0.3	
P 100 G 50	M 0.02	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	M 0.03	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
	M 0.04	1	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	
P 10 G 500	M 0.01	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
	M 0.02	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
	M 0.03	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
P 20 G 250	M 0.01	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
	M 0.02	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
	M 0.03	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
P 25 G 200	M 0.01	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
	M 0.02	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
	M 0.03	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
P 40 G 125	M 0.01	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
	M 0.02	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
	M 0.03	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
P 50 G 100	M 0.01	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
	M 0.02	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
	M 0.03	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	

	M 0.01	M 0.02	M 0.03	M 0.04	M 0.05	M 0.07	M 0.1	M 0.2	M 0.3
P 100 G 50	- - - - - - -	- - - - - -							
P 10 G 500	- - - - - - -	- - - - - -							
P 20 G 250	- - - - - -	- - - - - -	- - - - - -	- - - - - -	- - - - - -	- - - - - -	- - - - - -	- - - - - -	- - - - - -
P 25 G 200	- - - - - -	- - - - - -	- - - - - -	- - - - - -	- - - - - -	- - - - - -	- - - - - -	- - - - - -	- - - - - -
P 40 G 125	- - - - - -	- - - - - -	- - - - - -	- - - - - -	- - - - - -	- - - - - -	- - - - - -	- - - - - -	- - - - - -
P 50 G 100	- - - - - -	- - - - - -	- - - - - -	- - - - - -	- - - - - -	- - - - - -	- - - - - -	- - - - - -	- - - - - -

		P 20 G 250									
		M 0.01	M 0.02	M 0.03	M 0.04	M 0.05	M 0.07	M 0.1	M 0.2	M 0.3	
P 100 G 50	M 0.02	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.03	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.04	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.05	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.07	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
P 10 G 500	M 0.1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.01	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.02	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
P 20 G 250	M 0.03	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.04	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.05	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.07	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
P 25 G 200	M 0.2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.01	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.02	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.03	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
P 40 G 125	M 0.04	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.05	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.07	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
P 50 G 100	M 0.3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.01	0.5326	1	0.1303	1	0.2871	0.1136	0.0083 **	0.1136	0.0049 **	
	M 0.02	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
	M 0.03	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
	M 0.04	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	

	P 40 G 125									
	M 0.01	M 0.02	M 0.03	M 0.04	M 0.05	M 0.07	M 0.1	M 0.2	M 0.3	
P 100										
G 50										
	M 0.02	M 0.03	M 0.04	M 0.05	M 0.07	M 0.1	M 0.2	M 0.3		
P 10										
G 500										
	M 0.01	M 0.02	M 0.03	M 0.04	M 0.05	M 0.07	M 0.1	M 0.2	M 0.3	
P 20										
G 250										
	M 0.01	M 0.02	M 0.03	M 0.04	M 0.05	M 0.07	M 0.1	M 0.2	M 0.3	
P 25										
G 200										
	M 0.01	M 0.02	M 0.03	M 0.04	M 0.05	M 0.07	M 0.1	M 0.2	M 0.3	
P 40										
G 125										
	M 0.01	M 0.02	M 0.03	M 0.04	M 0.05	M 0.07	M 0.1	M 0.2	M 0.3	
P 50										
G 100										
	M 0.01	M 0.02	M 0.03	M 0.04	M 0.05	M 0.07	M 0.1	M 0.2	M 0.3	

	M 0.01	M 0.02	M 0.03	M 0.04	M 0.05	M 0.07	M 0.1	M 0.2
P 100 G 50	M 0.02	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.03	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.04	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.05	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.07	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
P 10 G 500	M 0.01	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.02	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.03	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.04	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.05	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
P 20 G 250	M 0.01	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.02	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.03	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.04	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.05	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
P 25 G 200	M 0.01	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.02	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.03	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.04	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.05	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
P 40 G 125	M 0.01	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.02	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.03	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.04	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	M 0.05	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
P 50 G 100	M 0.01	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.02	0.0859	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.03	0.2871	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.04	0.0558	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.05	0.3692	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.01	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.02	0.0645	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.03	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.04	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	M 0.05	1	1	1	1	1	1	1